

THE ROLE OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN IMPLEMENTING THE PRIORITY OF YOUTH EDUCATION IN THE CONDITIONS OF THE NEW UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: In this article, the relevance and priority of educational processes that should be instilled in young people in the implementation of educational system reforms in the conditions of New Uzbekistan and the role of foreign languages in these processes are expressed.

Key words: education, training, reform, youth, homeland, knowledge, country, independence, outlook, foreign language, school.

It is known to everyone that in the Republic of Uzbekistan, like all other fields, in order to reform the education system, to raise it to the level of development in line with today's world standards, our government and President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev are conducting very important work. As a result of the development of the continuous education system, it is envisaged that young people will become educated, physically healthy, work-loving, protecting the Motherland, possessing thorough knowledge, and most importantly, well-rounded people and mature personnel. For this, teaching foreign languages to students has become an urgent task of today. In this regard, youth education is also relevant. As the first President of Uzbekistan stated in the work "High spirituality - an invincible power", "Another important vital factor that directly affects the formation of spirituality is closely related to the education system. Therefore, the place and importance of education and upbringing in the formation of spirituality is considered great¹. It is known that the independence of our country created the ground for the implementation of fundamental changes in the field of national education. Taking into account the modern requirements, organizing the regular improvement of the educational processes of the general education subjects taught in the general secondary education system is one of the urgent tasks of today. At present, especially by teaching foreign languages to young people, wide opportunities have been created for the state to take its place in the world community. On the initiative of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, strict reforms in the field of education of the Republic of Uzbekistan began to be implemented. As a result, the educational system and content were improved based on market conditions. Currently, life itself requires the implementation of reforms in all spheres of our country, changing people's worldview, training mature and up-to-date specialists. In the republic, great importance is attached to strengthening the education system and harmonizing it with the requirements of the times. In this regard, it is important that the system of training, education and upbringing of specialists is closely connected with the requirements of reforms. One of the urgent issues facing us is the training of specialist

¹ Karimov I.A. "High spirituality is an invincible power." - T., "Spirituality" publishing house. 2008. 42 - p.

personnel who can meet the requirements of the time, improving education and all its structural structures based on state requirements. The main goal of the reforms being carried out in Uzbekistan is to create a healthy and well-educated generation in our country with high spiritual and moral qualities. In order to achieve this goal, under the leadership of President Sh. Mirziyoyev, the "O "Uzbek model" was implemented. In particular, obtaining certificates of proficiency in foreign languages is gaining relevance in increasing the potential of specialist personnel. Today's globalization processes, science and technology development, the need for an innovative society create many opportunities for young people. For this, young people who have thoroughly mastered foreign languages are the support of the state and society. To make quick decisions for young people to master the language, improve their speech? forming innovative thinking, increasing intellectual potential, and being loyal to national and universal values. For this, it is necessary to pay serious attention to the education of children from school. Chapter 4 of the "Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" adopted on January 15, 2022 focuses on several goals. Goal 41: "To create an additional 1.2 million student places in the public education system through the introduction of the National School Development Program", Goal 42: to improve curricula and textbooks by 2026 full review and implementation based on foreign experience", 43 - goal: "Step by step bringing the monthly salaries of qualified teachers to the equivalent of 1000 US dollars", 44 - the goal: to improve the quality of education in schools, to bring the knowledge and skills of pedagogues to the international level², etc. All of the above-mentioned highly important tasks are the attention and demand for improving the quality of school education. Currently, a teacher who knows a foreign language perfectly has received the monthly salary specified by the head of state.

It is not a secret to anyone that for a certain period of time we did not pay enough attention to education, as a result of which a number of unpleasant situations arose among the youth of our society. In order to prevent such unpleasant situations, the President of the Republic of Sh. On January 19, 2021, under the chairmanship of Mirziyoyev, a selector dedicated to the fundamental improvement of the system of spiritual and educational work was held, in which the President said, "We say that there will be no break in education. But this rule is not followed in the organization of spiritual and educational work. In this regard, kindergarten, school, higher education, neighborhood - each of them is working separately. Therefore, it is necessary to create a single system of spiritual and educational work, to clearly define the tasks of each responsible office and joint measures. If the body of society is the economy, then its soul and spirit are it's a destiny"³ - President Sh. Mirziyoyev emphasized.

Each subject taught in the educational system has its own importance and its own content - essence. The subject of Education, which was introduced into the educational process from the 2020-2021 academic year, is a combination of several subjects, and in its place acquires special importance and its own content - essence. The concept of "education" also means It is a concept of special importance for the lim system, and scientists and experts have expressed their opinions about it. Education is a practical pedagogical process aimed at

² Development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026. Chapter 4 - Fair social policy, development of human capital. www.strategy.uz.

³ Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Speech at the selector dedicated to the fundamental improvement of the system of spiritual and educational affairs. January 19, 2020. <https://youtu.be/ITINX2UdbQA>

forming certain physical, mental, moral and spiritual qualities in a person; a set of measures taken to ensure that a person has the characteristics necessary for living in society. Education is the most ancient and eternal value that ensures the humanity of a person. Without education, neither an individual nor a human society can exist. Because the values that ensure the existence of a person and society are passed from one generation to another only because of education.

In pedagogical literature, the term "Education" is used in broad and narrow senses. In a broad sense, education means the sum of all influences, activities, actions, and aspirations aimed at forming a human personality, ensuring his active participation in the production of society and social, cultural, educational life. In this understanding, education includes not only the educational work carried out in the family, school, children and youth organizations, but also the entire social system, its leading ideas, literature, art, cinema, radio, television, etc. Also, the concept of education in a broad sense includes education along with education.

In a narrow sense, education refers to pedagogical activities aimed at the development of physical development of a person, worldview, spiritual and moral image, and aesthetic taste. This is done by family and educational institutions and public organizations. Education and knowledge acquisition are not part of education in the narrow sense. But any upbringing exists only in close connection with education. Because in the process of education and knowledge acquisition, not only the knowledge of a person increases, but also the determination of moral and spiritual qualities is accelerated.

Education plays a crucial role in the life of any society and any country. A country that is not sufficiently engaged in the education of the young generation, in general, members of the society, is doomed to stagnation and crisis. After all, in order to grow and develop in any society, the production of material and spiritual wealth must continue to rise. For this, the young generation should be able to produce material and spiritual wealth at the level of their ancestors, and even better than them. In order to be able to form such material and spiritual abilities in the young generation, the society must have a system of educational processes that work continuously and effectively.

Education has been interpreted differently in different periods of social development. During the time of the Soviet Union, the ruling communist ideology demanded to approach education as a class and party phenomenon. That is why in a class society, education has only a class character and the education of different classes is opposed to each other. However, world science, especially the experience of Eastern education and Uzbek folk pedagogy, proved that education does not have a class aspect. Also, due to the pressure of communist ideology, social institutions were overestimated in education, genetic and biological characteristics were almost not taken into account in this process.

After Uzbekistan gained independence, the approach to education and related processes, based on a new and healthy pedagogical thinking, began to be decided. The non-scientific class party approach was abandoned in its interpretation. Special attention is paid to the nationality of education. For this, the riches of folk pedagogy, the pedagogical views of Uzbek thinkers are carefully studied.

We understand very well the truth of Abdulla Awlani's profound words: "Education is a matter of life or death for us, or salvation or destruction, or happiness or disaster." We all know the frustrations that arise when education issues are neglected, as well as the harmful consequences it causes. Education is not a separate process. Or the teacher who says that only

the family is responsible for education is mistaken. Together with the family, the team of the educational institution, the teachers must sacrifice their lives for education. It is necessary to get rid of the pain of desiring a rich world, clothes - yesterday, and engage in education. It is necessary for a modern teacher to carry out education and upbringing based on the requirements of today's times. Education should be inculcated in young people in every event organized based on the content of the topics covered in each subject and the features of the national mentality. As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan noted on January 28, 2022, at the meeting of the video selector on the issues of the development of school education, "Education is a matter of education - the future, life is a matter of death. Therefore, we have no right to delay the reforms in this area,"⁴ Sh. Mirziyoyev emphasized.

⁴ Sh. Mirziyoyev. Meeting of video selectors on the development of school education. <https://daryo.uz> January 28, 2022.

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